

Teaching experiences in the application of didactic processes in the Science and Technology Area

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Abstract— The objective was to analyse the teaching experience regarding the application of didactic processes in the area of Science and Technology at an educational institution in the year 2025. In the methodology the design of this research was phenomenological, with a hermeneutic study approach, as it focused on the understanding, exploration, and description of the participants' subjective experience, analyzing how they live and perceive such experiences, the population consisted of 42 teachers, the sample was made up of 10 key participants teaching fourth grade in a primary, the interview technique was the interview guide was the selected instrument, scientific rigor was ensured by considering the following criteria: transferability of the information, which refers to the fact that participants' information is focused on a specific context; credibility, which refers to internal validity and is ensured through faithful recording of the data; confirmability, which refers to the researcher's neutrality in interpretation; and auditability, meaning that the study can be reviewed. The study concluded that Science and Technology teachers partially develop the didactic processes of scientific inquiry, using limited strategies for problem formulation, hypothesis development, action planning, scientific representations and formalizations, evaluations, and reflections, as well as for the transfer and application of knowledge to real-world contexts. In contextualizing the problem, teachers take into account situations from everyday life, situations close to their daily lives, observation of their environment, cases and in the indicator asks questions it was considered relevant by several teachers that curiosity should be awakened to help them problematize, application of concepts, posing questions in a convenient way, project-based strategies for the development of these competencies.

Keywords— Teaching experiences, didactic processes, Science, Technology

I. INTRODUCTION

It was also considered that this research was important because it contributed to Sustainable Development Goal 4, which focuses on quality education. This goal, established by the State, seeks to ensure education for all that is not only inclusive but also equitable and of high quality—reaching everyone, especially those who need greater opportunities to achieve their integral development (United Nations [UN], 2024).

Organizations such as the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO] (2019), particularly those related to education, have identified the development of the Science and Technology area as fundamental. To this end, the application of scientific strategies aimed at fostering inquiry and research was promoted. Additionally, the incorporation of didactic processes specific to this area was considered essential for the development of these strategies.

In Latin American countries, the lack or near absence of continuous teacher training and the limited access to high-quality pedagogical resources have negatively affected teaching practices. This has led to inconsistencies in didactic strategies that could otherwise enhance student learning, especially among those facing disadvantages due to the lack of a proper education provided by well-prepared teachers often referred to as strength teachers.

In Spanish-speaking countries, efforts have been made to address most of the difficulties observed in classrooms, many of which have been constrained by limited use of these processes in their teaching practices, hindering their effective and practical implementation.

Learning based on inquiry and the development of didactic processes gives rise to active methodologies that promote quality science education. The constructivist approach encourages abstract thinking through critical analysis and scientific inquiry. Therefore, it is necessary for educational institutions to incorporate active, technological, and digital methodologies (Martínez & Rodríguez, 2023).

In this sense the question problem was: To address this issue, the following general research question was formulated: What is the teaching experience in the application of didactic processes in the area of Science and Technology at an educational institution in 2025? And the general objective was to analyze the teaching

experience regarding the application of didactic processes in the area of Science and Technology at an educational institution in the year 2025.

In international background studies, Harrell et al. (2022) conducted research with the aim of analyzing long-term research-based professional development to enhance teachers' pedagogical knowledge on topics related to Earth Sciences. The sample included 17 science teachers, and a mixed-methods approach with an exploratory design was used. Qualitative data were collected through reflective prompts and analyzed thematically. The findings aligned with and demonstrated the inclusion of four essential components of constructivism: prior knowledge; creation of cognitive dissonance (practice, field trips, pacing, scaffolding, technology, and collaboration/relationship); assessment (both informal and formal); and reflection. The study concluded that the reflective prompts demonstrated teachers' use of constructivist principles during lesson planning and implementation. This study contributes to the analysis of teachers' pedagogical reflection in the field of science education.

Zárate et al. (2021), in their research, analyzed strategies and didactic processes in the area of Science and Technology, including experiences in school laboratories and the analysis of inquiry-based activities. They concluded that this approach aims to promote students' development of scientific skills and knowledge construction, moving away from traditional teaching methodologies. The study contributes to the analysis of teaching strategies and didactic processes implemented by educators in the area of science and technology, and their impact on students.

Fuentes et al. (2021) conducted a study aimed at analyzing appropriate strategies for science teaching. Using a quantitative approach with a phenomenological design, they interviewed 16 teachers. The study concluded that teachers believe it is essential to develop science communication strategies and support the idea of organizing conferences to contribute to scientific dissemination. This study contributes to the analysis of communication-related strategies within the science education domain.

Similarly, Zurita (2020), in his article, aimed to understand how peer collaborative learning strengthened students' cognitive skill development. This study, conducted over a period of three years, used interviews as the main data collection method. It concluded that through this approach, students exchange knowledge while engaging with one another. The study contributes to the understanding of skills required for developing students' cognitive processes and highlights the impact of teaching on learning outcomes.

Álvarez (2020), in his research, aimed to analyze the use of teaching processes for the development of inquiry skills. The study used a qualitative approach with a phenomenological design. The findings highlighted the importance teachers place on developing students' cognitive abilities, emphasizing the need to strengthen teacher-student relationships. However, the study also concluded that few teachers promote or encourage the development of didactic processes in their classrooms, often focusing on low cognitive-demand questions and activities, and limiting instruction to memorization-based skills. This study contributes to the analysis of didactic processes employed by teachers in fostering scientific inquiry skills in students, offering a point of comparison for this research.

From a methodological perspective, it was necessary to analyze how didactic processes are developed within the area, both defined as the ability to construct knowledge through the implementation of innovative strategies used daily by teachers. These strategies, among other outcomes, generate knowledge, pose problems based on an understanding of the environment, and foster the development of specialized skills in the field of science (Hernández & Mendoza, 2018).

The theory of meaningful learning is based on the construction of new knowledge through the individual's existing experiences. Its primary emphasis lies in what the student already knows, highlighting the connection between prior knowledge and new learning, cognitive restructuring, and the construction of meaning. Secondly, it stresses the active role of the student, which implies that teachers must develop introductory strategies or guiding questions to help students make inferences about the new content. This

theory enables learning to be lasting and meaningful, as it contributes to the formation of reflective, critical students capable of solving real-life problems in their environment (Ausubel, 1983).

While there are other theories such as constructivism, learning is perceived as an active process in which prior knowledge is integrated with new knowledge, allowing for meaningful learning. The importance of constructivism lies in integrating and individualizing the relationships between learning and interaction processes, and solving contextualized problems. From his socio-constructivist approach, he emphasized the importance of the relationship between the cultural environment and social interaction through the construction of knowledge. He introduced the concept of the zone of proximal development, with the aim of describing the most effective way in which students learn, through their environment and a mediator. This theory emphasizes learning as the main factor in solving real problems, based on cooperation (Vygotsky, 1984).

Teaching experience refers to the set of didactic strategies, learning assessment practices, pedagogical approaches, the impact of implementing didactic processes, teacher resilience, and the training required by educators (González et al., 2021).

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According to the General Directorate of Regular Basic Education (2018), teaching experience in the area of Science and Technology is linked to a body of knowledge grounded in active engagement and experimentation. Therefore, it is essential to create supportive learning environments that allow students to manipulate, design, explore, and, most importantly, reflect on what they have done. In this sense, teaching experience refers to the set of didactic strategies, learning assessments, pedagogical practices, the effects of implementing didactic processes, teacher resilience, and the training required by educators (González et al., 2021).

Regarding the importance of didactic processes in Science and Technology, the National Fund for the Development of Peruvian Education [FONDEP] (2013) emphasized the need for students to acquire knowledge from an early age by using the resources available in their environment to construct their own learning. Furthermore, Slagus and Kelly (2022) pointed out that scientific thinking skills lead to the strengthening of didactic processes that are contextualized and connected to students' surroundings (Dawson & Venville, 2022).

In the category of didactic processes in the area of Science and Technology, the focus is on inquiry through scientific methods. Dewey (1938) stated that it is necessary to formulate the problem with supporting information that gives context to the issue. On the other hand, Palomino (2019) noted that the formulation of questions, experimentation, and especially the correct interpretation of the data obtained, contribute to the strengthening of investigative skills. Regarding problem formulation and the design of scientific strategies, Flórez and González (2021), as well as Duque (2020), agreed that problem formulation and the design of scientific strategies are fundamental elements in science teaching, particularly through the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) approach.

The proper implementation of didactic processes allows teachers to promote meaningful learning (Vélez et al., 2024). The correct application of these processes contributes to the creation of dynamic and participatory learning environments, where students remain motivated at all times and engaged in the development of the learning process. Thus, this implementation supports the development of competencies for a strong and effective student education (Fariás, 2022).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Design

The design of this research was phenomenological, with a hermeneutic study approach, as it focused on the understanding, exploration, and description of the participants' subjective experience, analyzing how they live and perceive such experiences. This approach relied exclusively on the individuals' lived experiences, without imposing external interpretations (Fuster, 2019).

2.2. Participants

The population was defined as the group of individuals, objects, events, or institutions that share common characteristics and are the subject of study (Hernández & Mendoza, 2018). To determine the sample, it was essential to clearly identify the target population. In this research, the population consisted of 42 teachers. The sample was made up of 10 key participants teaching fourth grade in a primary educational institution located in Callao. The inclusion criteria considered primary school teachers working in the area of science. Physical education teachers and those who did not provide informed consent were excluded.

2.3. Measuring instruments

For this research, the interview technique was used, and consequently, the interview guide was the selected instrument. This instrument was designed based on the categories and subcategories established for the categories of teaching experience and didactic processes in the area of Science and Technology. The instrument was validated through expert judgment. Scientific rigor was ensured by considering the following criteria: transferability of the information, which refers to the fact that participants' information is focused on a specific context; credibility, which refers to internal validity and is ensured through faithful recording of the data; confirmability, which refers to the researcher's neutrality in interpretation; and auditability, meaning that the study can be reviewed and commented on (Hernández & Mendoza, 2018).

2.4. Procedure

The procedure for data analysis involved conducting the interviews and subsequently transcribing them. Based on the results, data analysis and interpretation were carried out using Atlas.ti software, which enabled the identification of codes with relevant text segments and the conceptual development of the findings.

III. RESULTS

Regarding the results of the general objective was to analyze the teaching experience in the application of didactic processes of the competence inquires using scientific methods to construct knowledge in the area of Science and Technology, at an educational institution in 2025 an exhaustive analysis of the information was conducted. In this regard, the analysis of the specific objectives related to the teachers' experiences was carried out.

The report included interviews with 10 science and technology teachers. The teaching processes category and its subcategories were organized using ATLAS.TI software, enabling the identification of linked codes, complementing data triangulations and ensuring information analysis. The analyses included co-occurrence tables, and through their citations, the recurrence of the analyses performed was identified, selecting codes with more than 4.

TABLE I
CODES WITH CONCURRENCES

Codes	Co-occurrence
Situations in your context	5
Observation of the environment	3
Awaken curiosity	3
Situaciones reales, vivenciales	6
Real, experiential situations	3
Technological tools	3
Keywords	4
Identify and analyze situations	3
Collect data	8
Observation for evaluation	3
Formative assessment	4
Feedback	4

In the qualitative analysis of teachers' teaching processes, evidence of co-occurrence patterns was considered. Due to their frequency, these patterns should be taken into account in developing strategies to improve the problems encountered in teachers' experiences in their teaching practices in the area of Science and Technology. The predominant codes, with 8 co-occurrences, were collect data and with 6 co-occurrences were real or experiential situations. The codes that were regularly presented were Situations in their context with 5 co-occurrences. The least prevalent codes, with 4 co-occurrences, were the terms Keywords, Formative assessment, and Feedback, and with 3 co-occurrences, were Observation of the environment, Awakening curiosity, Relating cause and effect, Technological tools, Identifying and analyzing situations, and Observation for assessment.

Fig. 1 Unit of analysis of didactic processes in the Science and Technology Area and its seven subcategories

Fig. 1 presents the subcategories of the unit of analysis for the general objective, which include: problem formulation, hypothesis development, design of scientific strategies, development of action plans, scientific representations and formalizations, evaluations, and reflections, as well as transfer and application to real-life contexts. These subcategories are related to Kolb's (1984) experiential learning theory, which emphasizes learning by doing, allowing students to reinforce the internalization of concepts and prepare for problem-solving. Meanwhile, the project-based learning approach proposed by Dewey (1938) encouraged students to understand their environment and solve real-world situations, constantly promoting inquiry, observation, and, above all, teamwork.

Fig. 2 Emerging codes from the subcategory problem formulation

In Figure 2, it was found that teachers develop some isolated strategies that do not impact the development of the subcategory problem formulation. It was noted that, when contextualizing the problem, teachers take into account everyday life situations, scenarios close to students’ daily experiences, observation of their environment, and case studies. Regarding the indicator posing questions, several teachers considered it important to spark curiosity in order to help students engage in problematization, apply concepts, and appropriately formulate questions, as well as to use project-based strategies for the development of these competencies.

Fig. 3 Emerging codes from the subcategory hypothesis formulation.

Figure 3 shows that teachers develop some isolated strategies that do not have a significant impact on the development of hypothesis formulation, which involves identifying variables and establishing cause and effect. For this, the formulation of the problem must be generated by attempting to develop a solution through brainstorming, considering questions, taking real-life situations into account, and proposing hypotheses that aim to provide possible answers to the research.

Fig. 4 Emerging codes from the subcategory design of scientific strategies.

Figure 4 shows that teachers indicated that the design of strategies is integrated with technological tools, includes showing the source where the information was found, and involves the use of surveys, questionnaires, or a preference for interviews, careful observation, the use of keywords, or the implementation of inquiry-based learning strategies. Teachers must design experiments, collect data, and draw conclusions with a broad understanding of what is going to be investigated.

Fig. 5 Emerging codes from the subcategory development of an action plan

Figure 5, which addresses the development of an action plan, shows that to understand the inquiry methodology, drawings with step-by-step sequences on posters have been used, helping students figure out what they can do to respond and how to identify or analyze situations. Regarding the use of inquiry procedures, it is necessary to anticipate the materials and resources available. The topic should be chosen democratically, a problem prioritization matrix should be created, and questions should be formulated to address the issue. Students underline ideas, collect data, prepare a set of questions, and the process should be experiential, making it much more meaningful.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results obtained show a strong connection or similarity with those found by Álvarez (2020), who highlights the key role that teachers assign to the development of competencies and cognitive abilities, also emphasizing the need to strengthen the support and guidance between teacher and student. It is equally important to note that the conclusions reached by the author of the aforementioned study point out that only a few teachers actually develop the didactic processes of the Science and Technology Area in their learning sessions. On the contrary, they tend to emphasize rote learning and activities with low cognitive demand.

Likewise, Zárate et al. (2021), in their studies, concluded that it is necessary to strengthen and promote the development of scientific competencies and skills in students. To achieve this, traditional teaching methods must be left behind. The results are supported by the Scientific Inquiry approach. Cristóbal and García (2013) mentioned that learning science through inquiry means that students ask questions, and their curiosity to learn and discover something new guides their own learning. Scientific inquiry begins with observation; for this, the student uses all five senses, which allows them to explore and discover—this being the starting point for their investigations and the construction of their own knowledge. The scientific inquiry approach enables the student not only to be a learner but, at some point during the research process, to become an expert who can lead their own learning. In engaging with scientific inquiry, students used multiple ways of learning and connected them with processes such as exploration and experimentation.

Likewise, the findings are supported by Vygotsky's (1984) constructivist theory, which emphasized that the importance of constructivism lies in integrating and personalizing the relationships between learning and personal interaction processes, as well as in problem-solving within real and diverse contexts. The sociocultural theory of constructivism highlighted the role of society and social interaction in learning, which develops through interaction with others and the collective construction of knowledge—that is, in a social and culturally shared context. Vygotsky introduced the concept of the zone of proximal development and argued that students learn best through experimentation and with the guidance of a mediator, with learning being more effective when supported by their environment.

For his part, Bruner (1999) stated in his theory that knowledge is generated through social interactions and with the guidance of a facilitator, which aids in understanding. Considering that, science teaching has evolved considerably in recent decades, seeking increasingly effective methods that promote meaningful learning and the development of critical skills in students (Mendoza & Llor, 2022).

In relation to the first specific objective, it was found that in the phase of contextualizing the problem, teachers take into account everyday life situations, events close to students' daily experiences, observation of their environment, and real-life cases. Regarding the indicator "posing questions," several teachers considered it important to spark curiosity in order to help students problematize, apply concepts, and formulate appropriate questions. Strategies based on project-based learning were highlighted as key for the development of these competencies.

The results found are supported by the Situated Cognition Theory of Lave and Wenger (1991), who proposed that learning does not occur in isolation, especially in the sciences, as knowledge is intrinsically linked to experimentation in authentic situations. In these contexts, students must feel connected to the real world; in other words, learning should be contextualized and developed through interaction with other meaningful environments.

V. CONCLUSIONS

According to the general objective, it was concluded that Science and Technology teachers partially develop the didactic processes of scientific inquiry, using limited strategies for problem formulation, hypothesis development, action planning, scientific representations and formalizations, evaluations, and reflections, as well as for the transfer and application of knowledge to real-world contexts. In contextualizing the problem, teachers take into account situations from everyday life, situations close to their daily lives, observation of their environment, cases and in the indicator asks questions it was considered relevant by several teachers that curiosity should be awakened to help them problematize, application of concepts, posing questions in a convenient way, project-based strategies for the development of these competencies.

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